

A Thermodynamic Study (Polarographically) of the Reaction Between Cobalt(III) Amines and Some Schiff Bases Derived from Amino Acids

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The stability constants of the pentaammine cobalt(III) and tetraammine cobalt(III) complexes with Schiff bases have been determined by the polarographic method. Thermodynamic parameters: ΔH , ΔS and ΔG have been evaluated. The decrease in stability of the complexes has been assigned to lengthening of the amino acid chain.

STUDIES on the metal complexes of Schiff bases provide valuable information about biological transamination reactions and metal-pyridoxal-amino acid systems^{1,2}. Therefore, in an earlier communication³ we had reported complex formation between penta and tetraammine cobalt (III) ions and some Schiff bases. These studies have now been extended to the polarographic determination of the stability constant (K) (at different temperatures), enthalpy change (ΔH) and entropy change (ΔS) associated with these reactions.

Experimental

The Schiff bases were prepared by the method of Dietrich et al as described by Heinert and Martell⁴, from salicylaldehyde or *o*-vanillin and amino acids (glycine, aspartic acid, glutamic acid). The various Schiff bases were prepared by condensation of salicylaldehyde with glycine (S-Gly), aspartic acid (S-A) and glutamic acid (S-G) and vanillin with glycine (V-Gly), aspartic acid (V-A) and glutamic acid (V-G). Salicylaldehyde (BDH, L.R.) was purified by distillation prior to use. Glycine, aspartic acid, glutamic acid and vanillin were A.R. grade (BDH) reagents. Chloropentaammine cobalt(III) chloride⁵ and cis-chloro-aquotetraammine cobalt(III) chloride⁶ were prepared from cobalt chloride. All solutions were prepared with water distilled from alkaline permanganate solution and redistilled twice.

Polarograms were recorded with a Cambridge pen recording polarograph using a d.m.e. of $m^{3/5}t^{1/5} = 3.75 \text{ mg}^{3/5} \text{ sec}^{-1/5}$. The solutions were held at 60° for 1 hr and then allowed to equilibrate at 30° for 1/2 hr. The requisite amount of supporting electrolyte (CH_3COONa or LiCl) was then added and the solutions deaerated by bubbling purified nitrogen for about 10 min before recording the polarograms. All measurements were carried

out in a constant temperature water bath. The values of kinetic parameters were determined from the polarograms of the solutions containing $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ Co(III) ions and various amounts of Schiff bases using Koutecky's⁷ method as extended by Meites and Israel⁸.

Results and Discussion

Interaction of chloropentaammine or cis-chloro-aquotetraammine cobalt(III) chloride with the Schiff bases was found to give 1:1 complexes⁹. The Schiff bases are monodentate in the pentaammine complexes and bidentate in the tetraammine complexes³. Polarographic reduction of these complexes³ was found to be diffusion controlled but irreversible in nature. The polarograms of the complexes were recorded in various supporting electrolytes, viz., $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NBr}$, Na_2SO_4 , CH_3COONa , KCl , LiClO_4 and LiCl . Well defined waves were obtained with CH_3COONa and LiCl . Similar results were obtained with both the electrolytes.

The stability constants of the Schiff base complexes (Tables 1 and 2) were calculated from the polarographic data at different temperatures (25, 30, 35, 40 and 15, 20, 25, 30°) with the help of modified Lingane's method for an irreversible process⁹.

The following relationships were used to derive the thermodynamic parameters:

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K$$

$$\ln \frac{K_2}{K_1} = \frac{\Delta H}{R} \left(\frac{T_2 - T_1}{T_1 \cdot T_2} \right)$$

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T \Delta S$$

The values of free energy of formation (ΔG), enthalpy changes (ΔH) and entropy changes (ΔS)

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TABLE 1—ELECTROCHEMICAL KINETIC PARAMETERS FROM POLAROGRAPHIC CURRENT POTENTIAL CURVES FOR SCHIFF BASE + CIS-CHLOROQUOTETRAAMMINE COBALT(III) CHLORIDE SYSTEM
SUPPORTING ELECTROLYTE.....0.1M CH₃COONa
CONCENTRATION OF COMPLEX.....1 × 10⁻³M

Complex of cis-chloro- aquotetra- ammine Co(III) with	Temp. °K	K _{r,h} ^o cm/sec (formal rate constant)	αn	D _o ^{1/2}	(a) log K	-ΔG k cal/mole	ΔS k cal/mole	ΔH k cal/mole
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
(S-Gly)	288	7.6 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.35	1.09 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.14	5.48		
	293	5.1 × 10 ⁻⁷	0.24	1.10 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.25	5.74	63.20	12.70
	298	5.2 × 10 ⁻⁷	0.21	0.58 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.49	6.17		
	303	5.6 × 10 ⁻⁷	0.26	1.6 × 10 ⁻⁵	4.61	6.44		
(S-A)	288	7.7 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.50	1.81 × 10 ⁻⁵	3.18	4.22		
	293	1.1 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.42	0.91 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.34	4.51	51.30	10.50
	298	3.4 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.55	2.5 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.50	4.80		
	303	6.7 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.59	0.91 × 10 ⁻³	3.58	4.99		
(S-G)	288	7.3 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.56	0.64 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.90	3.85		
	293	2.6 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.47	0.67 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.95	3.98	25.63	3.52
	298	3.1 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.49	1.10 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.00	4.11		
	303	1.2 × 10 ⁻⁷	0.36	3.20 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.05	4.25		
(V-Gly)	288	2.4 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.43	3.92 × 10 ⁻⁵	3.56	4.72		
	293	4.7 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.48	1.66 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.59	4.84	24.90	2.44
	298	1.1 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.36	4.38 × 10 ⁻⁵	3.62	4.97		
	303	1.7 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.36	6.77 × 10 ⁻⁵	3.65	5.09		
(V-A)	288	4.5 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.32	0.94 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.54	4.69		
	293	5.9 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.34	2.23 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.58	4.83	29.34	3.77
	298	1.1 × 10 ⁻⁷	0.24	0.41 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.62	4.97		
	303	2.8 × 10 ⁻⁷	0.26	1.99 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.67	5.11		
(V-G)	288	5.8 × 10 ⁻⁷	0.31	5.60 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.13	2.82		
	293	6.3 × 10 ⁻⁷	0.27	4.31 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.26	3.05	45.67	10.31
	298	6.7 × 10 ⁻⁷	0.25	7.91 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.41	3.30		
	303	7.3 × 10 ⁻⁷	0.27	7.56 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.53	3.53		

(a) Each value is a mean of three readings.
1 cal/mole = 4.1840 joules/mole.

TABLE 2—ELECTROCHEMICAL KINETIC PARAMETERS FROM POLAROGRAPHIC CURRENT-POTENTIAL CURVE FOR SCHIFF BASE + MONOCHLOROPENTAAMMINE CO(III) CHLORIDE SYSTEM
SUPPORTING ELECTROLYTE.....0.1M CH₃COONa
CONCENTRATION OF THE COMPLEX.....1 × 10⁻³M

Complex of chloropenta- ammine Co(III) with	Temp. °K	K _{r,h} ^o cm/sec (formal rate constant)	αn	D _o ^{1/2}	(a) log K	-ΔG k cal/mole	ΔS k cal/mole	ΔH k cal/mole
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
(S-Gly)	298	1.2 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.59	4.48 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.47	0.65		
	303	4.0 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.54	4.59 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.63	0.88	33.18	9.21
	308	8.9 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.47	4.54 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.71	1.01		
	313	2.6 × 10 ⁻⁷	0.41	7.28 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.79	1.14		
(S-A)	298	6.3 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.54	1.14 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.62	3.60		
	303	1.5 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.51	3.14 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.68	3.74	24.48	3.68
	308	3.4 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.47	2.15 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.72	3.86		
	313	5.9 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.47	3.74 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.75	3.96		
(S-G)	298	7.0 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	0.77	1.24 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.51	2.07		
	303	9.8 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.56	0.88 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.63	2.27	29.63	6.72
	308	7.3 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.65	2.65 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.71	2.43		
	313	8.6 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.61	2.10 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.75	2.52		
(V-Gly)	298	8.6 × 10 ⁻¹¹	0.75	1.11 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.33	4.57		
	303	1.6 × 10 ⁻¹¹	0.71	0.88 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.38	4.72	32.81	5.18
	308	5.4 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	0.52	0.61 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.43	4.87		
	313	1.5 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.47	0.70 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.53	5.08		
(V-A)	298	6.1 × 10 ⁻¹²	0.71	1.48 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.60	3.57		
	303	1.8 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	0.59	4.80 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.67	3.72	24.88	3.84
	308	4.7 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	0.56	6.75 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.70	3.80		
	313	6.9 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	0.56	5.49 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.71	3.95		
(V-G)	298	6.6 × 10 ⁻⁹	0.43	2.39 × 10 ⁻⁶	1.63	2.24		
	303	2.4 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.36	3.37 × 10 ⁻⁶	1.69	2.36	24.10	4.93
	308	2.6 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.33	0.58 × 10 ⁻⁶	1.75	2.49		
	313	6.1 × 10 ⁻⁸	0.42	2.28 × 10 ⁻⁶	1.81	2.61		

(a) Each value is a mean of three readings.
1 cal/mole = 4.1840 joules/mole.

are summarised in Tables 1 and 2. No statistical estimation of uncertainty in the values of thermodynamic parameters was done due to inadequate number of experimental data.

The values of log K are positive in all cases. In comparing the complex-formation properties of these Schiff bases, it is observed that the Schiff base of glycine forms the most stable complexes, the order in decreasing stability being: Glycine > Aspartic acid > Glutamic acid. This decrease in stability is due to the increase in chain length of the α -amino acids. Similar results have been reported by previous workers^{10,11}. The S-Gly complex with monochloropentaammine shows an anomalous behaviour with the value of log K being very low. However, it appears to be difficult to assign any specific reason for its low stability. From Tables 1 and 2 it is further evident that all these reactions are endothermic and the entropy changes (ΔS) are positive, whereby the entropy term strongly favours complex formation¹².

Determination of Kinetic Parameters :

Since the waves are irreversible in both the systems, the values of transfer coefficient (αn) and formal rate constant ($K_{f,h}^\circ$) for the electrode reactions have been determined under various conditions by Koutecky's method⁷ as extended by Meits and Israel⁸ using the following equations :

$$E_{d,e} = E_{1/2} - \frac{0.0542}{\alpha n} \left[\log \frac{i}{i_d - i} - 0.546 \log t \right]$$

where,

$$E_{1/2} = \frac{0.05915}{\alpha n} \log \frac{1.349 K_{f,h}^\circ}{D^{1/2}}$$

The values of $D^{1/2}$ were calculated using the Ilkovic Equation. The values of $K_{f,h}^\circ$ and $D^{1/2}$ are given in Tables 1 and 2.

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